

CONCLUSIONS / CONSIDERATIONS

- The FIREglobulus project promoted the creation of the scientific basis for the technological development of prescribed fire in blue gum plantations.
- The combination of laboratory and field burn trials succeeded in providing answers to the research questions
- The experimental program succeeded in developing user-friendly relationships to predict fuel loading, fuel moisture content, the likelihood of fire spread, fire behaviour characteristics, fuel consumption and fire-induced tree injury
- The results allow defining the limits for the use of fire and the corresponding environmental conditions that meet treatment objectives
- The results will be materialized as a self-sufficient predictive chain, providing operational burning guidelines and quantitative prescriptions to achieve specific treatment objectives

FIREglobulus project is a partnership between GIFF S.A. and UTAD - University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro, co-funded by the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) through the Regional Operational Programme of North.

GIFF SA is a Portuguese private company specialized in forest fires prevention and control, the use of fire applied to the management, conservation and protection of natural areas against forest fire, and forest management. The company assists its clients in the protection of forests from wildfire damage. Through a technical staff specialized in fire prevention and suppression and in forest management, the company guarantees its customers a realistic and objective, knowledge-based approach to the potential of fire spread into their properties, and measures to decrease and mitigate the corresponding risk. Among other services, the company plans and carries out prescribed burning operations and provides specialized technical training fitting the needs of its customers.

APPLICATIONS

FIRE HAZARD REDUCTION
REDUCTION OF POST-HARVEST SLASH FUELS
SITE PREPARATION FOR TREE PLANTING

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FIREglobulus

USE OF PRESCRIBED FIRE IN BLUE GUM STANDS

- The severity of forest fires, the representativeness, flammability and economic importance of eucalypts, and the success of prescribed fire in fuel management, advised exploratory studies on the possibility of using it to mitigate the risk of fire in eucalypt plantations.
- The FIREglobulus project seeks to create a scientific basis for the technological development of prescribed fire in Eucalyptus globulus plantations. The management of biomass fuel in forest plantations of highly flammable species is an essential component of their sustainable management, to limit wildfire potential and allow effective fire-control operations under extreme weather conditions, reducing the ecological impact of fire and increasing the value of salvaged wood.
- Destructive sampling was carried out to develop user-friendly ways of estimating fuel loading and the moisture content of dead fuels. We studied the behaviour and effects of autumn to spring experimental fires in several eucalypt stands, complemented by laboratory trials to assess the sustainability of fire spread, the consumption of woody fuels and relative effect of fuel accumulation on fire behaviour.
- Fire behaviour characteristics were related with fuel complex descriptors and other environmental factors, the performance of existing fire behaviour models was assessed, and a chain of predictive relations linking the fire environment (weather, fuel), fire behaviour, and fire impacts on fuels and trees was developed.
- The results will allow operational guidelines and decision support to prescribed fire use, such that fuel-hazard reduction targets are met without adverse effects on eucalypt trees.

ASSESSMENT OF DEAD FUEL MOISTURE

- Prompt, straightforward and reliable estimation of dead fine fuel moisture is essential for operational planning of prescribed burning, given its influence on the sustainability of fire spread, fire behaviour characteristics characteristics and fuel consumption.

- A model that allows to estimate the moisture content of surface litter in blue gum stands was developed, function of temperature and relative humidity (through vapor pressure deficit), FFMC (Fine Fuel Moisture Code of the Canadian FWI system) and open wind speed at 10-m height. The model was shown to be adequate after being tested in independent experimental fires.

- As an alternative a user-friendlier model was developed that employs the number of days since last rainfall in lieu of the FFMC.

- The moisture contents of woody fuels (diameter ≥ 6 mm and < 25 mm), elevated bark and bark at the tree base can all be estimated from litter moisture content.

Prediction of surface litter moisture content in blue gum stands as a function of air temperature (T), relative humidity (RH) and FFMC

FFMC	T(°C)	100				125				150				175			
		40	50	60	70	40	50	60	70	40	50	60	70	40	50	60	70
70		25	26	29	32	23	25	27	30	22	23	25	28	20	22	24	27
75		23	24	26	30	21	23	25	28	20	21	23	26	19	20	22	25
80		21	22	24	27	19	21	23	25	18	20	21	24	17	18	20	22
85		19	20	22	25	18	19	21	23	17	18	20	22	16	17	18	21
90		17	19	20	23	16	18	19	21	15	16	18	20	14	15	17	19
95		16	17	19	21	15	16	18	20	14	15	16	18	13	14	15	17

Adjustment of surface litter moisture content in blue gum stands as a function of 10-m height wind speed.

Wind speed 10m (km/h)	Fine fuel moisture content (%)																					
	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32
1	12	14	16	18	20	22	25	27	28	31	33	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32
2	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32
3	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32
4	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32
5	12	14	16	18	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	12	14	16	18	19	21	23	25	27	29	31
6	12	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	12	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31
7	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	28	30	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	28	30
8	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	24	26	28	30	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	24	26	28	30
9	11	13	15	17	19	20	22	24	26	28	30	11	13	15	17	19	20	22	24	26	27	29
10	11	13	15	16	18	20	22	24	26	27	29	11	13	15	16	18	20	22	24	26	27	29
11	11	13	14	16	18	20	22	24	25	27	29	11	13	14	16	18	20	22	24	25	27	29
12	11	13	14	16	18	20	21	23	25	27	29	11	13	14	16	18	20	21	23	25	27	29
13	11	12	14	16	18	19	21	23	25	26	28	11	12	14	16	18	19	21	23	25	26	28
14	10	12	14	16	17	19	21	23	24	26	28	10	12	14	16	17	19	21	23	24	26	28
15	10	12	14	15	17	19	21	22	24	26	28	10	12	14	15	17	19	21	22	24	26	28

- Out of prescription
- Marginal conditions
- Regular
- Marginal conditions

FUEL LOADING ASSESSMENT

- Fuel loading (t/ha) estimation is a requisite to predict fire behaviour characteristics.

- An operational model was developed that estimates the total fuel loading in a stand from the average depth of litter.

- Fine fuel loading (< 6mm diameter) plays the major role in fire spread and is estimated from total fuel loading.

Relationships between litter depth and fuel loadings (total and fine) in blue gum stands

FIRE BEHAVIOUR CHARACTERISTICS

- The rate of spread of a fire is the most basic descriptive variable of its behaviour. Combined with fuel consumption it determines flame size, which in turn expresses energy release and is equivalent to fireline intensity.

- Experimental laboratory fires were used to evaluate the relative changes in fire spread rate and intensity as a function of fine fuel loading.

- Prediction of fire spread rate in blue gum plantations is based on fire spread direction, 1.5-m wind speed, surface litter moisture content, litter depth and terrain slope.

- Fuel consumption is predicted from pre-burn litter depth and DMC, the Duff Moisture Code of the Canadian FWI system.

- Flame length is estimated from fire spread rate and surface litter moisture content and can be converted to fireline intensity, the overall descriptor of "what a fire does"

- litter depth 2 cm
- litter depth 4 cm
- litter depth 6 cm
- litter depth 8 cm

FIRE BEHAVIOUR ASSESSMENT

FIRE SPREAD SUSTAINABILITY

- Experimental laboratory fires were used to identify the relevant variables (surface litter moisture content, litter depth, fire spread direction – forward or backward) and their thresholds for self-sustained fire spread.

- Model performance was validated in independent experimental prescribed burns in blue gum plantations.

Analysis of the sustainability of fire spread in blue gum litter

TREE DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

- The fuel reduction goal should be attained without inflicting damage to the crop trees. Tree were monitored after the experimental fires and their condition (dead (red), live with basal/trunk sprouting (yellow), live without sprouting (green)) was modelled from diameter at breast height, stem height char and the DMC. Stem height char is a function of flame length.

- Depending on their size, trees in the prescribed burnt stands grew more 21% to 34% (in diameter) than trees in the unburned control plots